

Nexus Between Deposit Money Bank Performance and Non-Oil Sector Output Growth: Experience from Nigeria and South Africa

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
24 July 2025

ABSTRACT

This study focused on investigating the nexus between deposit money bank performance and the non-oil sector nexus with emphasis on Nigeria and South Africa using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. Some sets of annual time series data ranging from 1990 to 2020 were utilized. Performance indicators of deposit money banks like as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) are used to capture the effects of deposit money banks on the non-oil sector. In addition, non-oil sector performance indicators such as agricultural value added (AVD), employment in agriculture (EIAG), manufacturing value added % of GDP – MVA, services value added (SVA) – a percentage of GDP, were employed as the measures of non-oil sector performance; while the control variables include interest rate (INTR) and exchange rate (EXR). In addition, the result of the long-run bound test shows that a long-run relationship also exists between deposit money bank performance and the non-oil sector. Evidence from the main findings in the ARDL results indicates that there is a positive long-run relationship between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector performance. In the short run, the speed of adjustments from short-run to long-run for models 1 – 3 measured the speed of adjustments. The results of the country's specific effects show that the deposit money bank has negative effects on the non-oil sector in Nigeria but has a significant of the South African non-oil sector. Thus, policies like economic diversification and enhancement of macroeconomic and institutional quality were recommended.

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KEYWORDS: Deposit Money Bank Performance and Non-Oil Sector Output Growth

1 INTRODUCTION

Non-oil sector of an economy has been a major contributor of countries economic growth and development. In most cases, it serves as the source of employment, generates a static supply of raw materials for production and exports. Deposit-taking banks have also been noteworthy in promoting the overall economic activities of all sectors of the economy, in terms of providing funds to individuals, industries, firms, as well as micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) for production and manufacturing purposes. A deposit money bank plays an important function in the development and growth of a nation's economy. The foremost role carried out by deposit money banks is to ensure there is an adequate flow of money to service deficit sectors of the economy and facilitate the movement of funds amongst economic units. For instance, until the discovery of crude oil in Africa, the

agricultural sector was the most viable in most African countries. During this period, Nigeria and South Africa were among the highest exporters of agricultural produce. Africa is endowed with lots of mineral resources ranging from Crude oil, Tin, Lead, and Iron ore, Coal, a few but to mention, and the Non-oil sector has been the bedrock of economic growth and development in the African continent, and deposit money bank performance is of important to the growth of all sectors of the economy. Over the years, many researchers and academics, such as Okezie and Azubike (2017) and Chima (2017), have pointed out that the non-oil sector has helped, in no small measure, to boost the incomes of billions of people in Africa.

Deposit money in banks in improving non-oil sector output growth is immeasurable; it plays an important role in the financial system and the economy. As a key component of the

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financial system, banks allocate funds from savers to borrowers in an efficient manner. Deposit money banks also provide specialised financial services, which reduce the cost of obtaining information on both savings, borrowing opportunities and investment services. These financial

services help in making the overall economy more efficient and extend more funding opportunities to firms and micro, medium and small enterprises (MSMEs) in the non-oil sectors of the economy.

Fig 1: Non-Oil Sectoral Output Growth in Nigeria and South Africa

Source: World Bank’s World Development Indicators.

The overall sectoral analysis of the Agricultural, Manufacturing and Services sectors shows that the services sector’s output growth performed better, followed by the manufacturing sector and the agricultural sector (see Fig. 1). Indeed, the contribution of output growth in the agricultural sector, the manufacturing sector and the services sector in South Africa surpasses that of Nigeria. Remarkably, the contribution of agricultural output of South Africa in 2013, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2020 grew far beyond output growth in Nigeria. In the like manner, comparing the output growth of the manufacturing and services sectors, South African output growth was observed to be greater than Nigeria. According to the 2020 report of the nation’s encyclopaedia, over 70 per cent of the Nigerian population predominantly engaged in the agricultural sector at a subsistent level. This stems from the fact that the Nigerian economy basically relied upon the credit of crude oil revenue for running national affairs, funding budgets and infrastructural development. South Africa, on the other hand, has more commercial lame light in terms of contribution of the agricultural sector. The agricultural sector contributed about 10% of GDP in 2019, which made her export earnings stand at \$10.7 billion in 2019. These great contributions of agricultural sector gave birth to the mass production of products such as Citrus, Wine, Table Grapes, Corn and Wool, Nuts, Sugar, Mohair, Apples and Pears etc. In the light of this, it was argued that an

increase in output growth of agricultural produce would definitely increase production in both the manufacturing and services sectors by providing enormous raw materials for production (see Wang et al., 2010).

Amidst the outcomes of the previous empirical findings, this study, however, will evaluate the nexus between non-oil sector output growth and deposit money bank experience from Nigeria and South Africa from 1990 to 2020. Much emphasis will be laid on how each country’s agricultural sector, manufacturing sector and services sector are being influenced by the deposit money bank. In addition, the study further investigated the country-specific effect of the deposit money bank effect on non-oil sector performance in Nigeria and South Africa; thus, this serves as a value addition to the study. This study also employed return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) as the measure of deposit money bank performance; agricultural value added (AVD), manufacturing value added (MVA), services value added (SVA), employment in services sector (EIS) % of total employment and trade in services (TIS) as measures of non-oil sector; while control for interest rate (INTR) and inflation rate (INF). However, other sections of this study will be organised as follows. Section 2 will harness the evaluation of non-oil sector output growth and deposit money bank performance in Nigeria and South Africa. Section 3 deals with literature reviews, and Section 4 deals with research methodology and

model specifications. Section 5 houses the presentation and interpretations of the results, and the summary of findings, policy recommendations and conclusion was discussed in Section 6.

2. EVALUATION OF NON-OIL SECTOR OUTPUT GROWTH AND DEPOSIT MONEY BANK PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

The support which all sectors of the economy derive from the performance of the deposit money bank cannot be overemphasised. The deposit money bank serves as a dependable channel of wealth creation and provision of funds

for the real/non-oil sector of the economy. It spurs the non-oil sector with ubiquitous financial opportunities, which include the provision of credits, lending of funds to deficit units, ease in financial transactions, payment for goods and services, and receipt of payments from customers. It aids Firms, industries, and micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) performance by increasing their ease of doing business as they would always need to expand their plants, production activities, and procurement of machinery for their operation. Figure 1 below shows the performance of the deposit money bank in Nigeria and South Africa in 2020.

Fig 1: Interplay between Non-Oil Sector Output Growth and Deposit Money Bank in Nigeria and South Africa

Source: World Bank’s World Development Indicator (WDI). Note: ROA=return on assets; ROE=return on equity; AVD = agricultural sector value added; MVA = manufacturing sector value added; and SVA=services sector value added.

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between deposit money bank performance indicators—return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE)—and non-oil sector output growth indicators, including agricultural value added (AVD), manufacturing value added (MVA), and services value added (SVA). The data reveal that South Africa recorded a higher return on assets compared to Nigeria. However, Nigeria outperformed South Africa in terms of return on equity and manufacturing value added. Notably, Nigeria’s agricultural value added was significantly lower than that of South Africa, suggesting that South Africa’s agricultural sector was more robust in 2020. While both countries had comparable performance in the manufacturing sector, Nigeria had a slight edge. Conversely, the services sector in Nigeria lagged behind that of South Africa. This disparity reflects the heavy reliance of Nigeria’s economy on crude oil revenues, which has hindered the development of other critical sectors. In contrast, South Africa showed stronger performance in its return on assets, agricultural output, and services sector. In light of these observations, Manasseh et al. (2024) advocate for comprehensive development across all non-oil sectors—

agriculture, industry, construction, services, manufacturing, and trade—as these sectors have demonstrated significant contributions to output growth during both economic booms and recessions. Both Nigeria and South Africa are therefore encouraged to prioritize economic diversification to ensure sustainable growth.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1 Theoretical Review

3.1.1 The Supply-Led Finance Theory

This theory was proposed by Patrick in 1966 based on the assumption that “finance from the deposit money bank is the most important variable for real sector growth”. Supply-led finance theory is growth-inducing in nature, which means that finance is the most significant factor for promoting economic development. Furthermore, the theory held that “the provision of funds by financial institutions through the extension of credit to business firms in all sectors of the economy to support the creation, transformation, expansion of industries and developmental projects, would thus enhance the growth potentials of the economy”. It is pertinent to say

that deposit money banks through financial intermediation role helps in channelling the limited resources from surplus units to the deficit units, which leads to efficient allocation of resources thereby, leading all other economic sectors in the process of production of goods and services. The supply-led finance theory, emphasized that finance and economic development are conjoint and causal, suggesting that economic development have bidirectional causality.

3.1.2 Wicksell Theory of Lending

The Kunt-Wicksell Theory of lending, proposed in 1901 on quantity theory of money, compared the marginal productivity of capital with the cost of borrowing money by businesses in all sectors of the economy (Weise, 2006). In his opinion, Wicksell argued that “if interest rate of borrowing money was below the natural rate of return on capital, entrepreneurs would borrow at the money rate to purchase capital goods”. This would lead to increased demand for all types of resources and, in turn, their prices. Contrariwise, “if the interest rate of borrowing money was above the natural rate of return on capital, entrepreneurs would sell the capital goods and hold money”. This would lead to a lower demand for money and in turn the cost of borrowing. Furthermore, Wicksell connected the rate of interest with the production gap. The production gap represented the variance between what ought to be produced and what is produced. This theory gives a direct connection between the demand for the cost of money and output in a country. It equally shows how interest rates affect borrowing, which in turn affects the purchase of capital goods and how production is affected. If interest rates are higher than the natural rate of return, borrowing will reduce therefore reducing economic growth as a result of low investment. On the contrary, if the rate of interest is lower than the natural rate of return, then more borrowing will take place and this will spur growth of all sectors of the economy through more investment (Weise, 2006).

3.2 Empirical Review

Hassan and Amin (2023) analysed the impact of banking performance on economic growth in Saudi Arabia for the period 2000-2018 by focusing on 12 banks and using a panel auto regression distributed lag approach. The results showed that banking performance has long-run and short-run effects on economic growth. Alkhazaleh (2017) conducted research for Jordan and revealed that banking performance indicators, especially profitability, deposits credits, are positively related to economic growth. Nahidul Sm et al. (2019), using a panel data regression model and focusing on 16 commercial banks of Bangladesh, found that the financial performance of the banking sector has a significant impact on economic growth in Bangladesh for the period 2008-2017. Hajara and Rinosha (2022) proved that the financial performance of the banking sector has a positive and significant impact on Sri Lanka's economic growth in both the short and long term for the period from 1998 to 2019. Zeqiraj et al. (2019) and Topaloğlu and Ege (2020) and Ferreira (2013) conducted a study for

European Union countries and found that bank performance has a positive effect on economic growth. Similarly, F and F (2024) indicated that an increase in the return on assets (ROA) of banks generated a notable increase in economic growth across 16 countries in Central and Eastern Europe for the period 1999-2020. Reddy et al. (2023) and Alam et al. (2021) showed that there is a correlation between banking sector performance and economic growth in India. Barfi (2020), using a panel generalised linear model, found that banking sector performance negatively affects economic growth in 7 East African countries from 1996 to 2017. Ledhem and Mekidiche (2020) analyzed the relation between the financial performance of Islamic finance and economic growth, using the CAMELS model and focusing on Islamic banks in Malaysia, Indonesia, Brunei, Turkey and Saudi Arabia. It was found that the financial performance of Islamic finance through profitability has a significant positive effect on economic growth. Ali et al. (2022) found that bank profitability has a positive short- and long-term effect on economic growth, by focusing on six countries in the GCC region from 2000 to 2019. These results support the notion that authorities should promote bank profitability to stimulate economic growth. Hammami and Smida (2022) found a positive long-term relationship between the banking sector and economic growth in Tunisia. The study indicates that it is indeed crucial to develop a robust banking sector to strengthen economic growth. It recommends that governments avoid excessive deficits and borrowing from the private sector and continue the restrictive monetary policy on the part of the Tunisian Central Bank.

Hamdaoui and Cancelo (2024) indicated a positive correlation between the banking sector and economic growth in Spain, France and Romania from 2000 to 2020. The study underscores the central role of the banking sector in promoting economic expansion. Kale and Eken (2022) revealed a limited positive relationship between bank efficiency and economic growth in the OECD countries for the period 2011-2019, by using the SBM model. Nguyen (2022), using an ARDL-based multivariate regression technique, found a positive long-term impact of banking development on Vietnam's economic growth from 1990 to 2020. Ibrahim and Abdalla (2020), using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model of cointegration, found the absence of a long-run association between banking development and economic growth in Sudan from 1980 to 2017. Other studies have proven that the development of the banking sector has a major impact on economic growth. Manasseh et al. (2025) examined the long-run effects of financial technology and innovation on bank performance in ECOWAS from 1997 to 2022 using the ARDL technique. The study found that fintech tools like mobile and internet banking, along with innovations such as POS and mobile payments, significantly improved ROA and ROE. The authors recommend supportive regulatory frameworks to

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harness fintech’s potential for boosting bank performance. Manasseh et al. (2024) explored the impact of technological innovation on bank performance across 40 emerging markets from 2000 to 2021. The study found strong positive correlations and long-run relationships between innovation and performance, confirmed through ARDL and GMM analyses. It recommends strengthening tech infrastructure and using digital tools to reach underbanked populations for enhanced banking outcomes. Obiora et al. (2022) examine how economic development affects banking performance in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) compared to developed economies between 1981 and 2018. Their findings show that while development improves credit supply and reduces nonperforming loans in SSA, persistent regional banking inefficiencies and rising interest rates undermine progress. The study recommends targeted policy reforms to address structural weaknesses across the SSA’s banking systems.

In Nigeria, Daramola (2024) explored the link between deposit money banks' (DMBs) credit and non-oil exports in Nigeria from 1986 to 2022 using ARDL analysis. The study found a significant positive relationship between DMBs’ credit and exchange rates, while lending and inflation rates had negative impacts on non-oil exports. Despite the lack of causality between credit and exports, the findings underscore the need for macroeconomic stability and supportive policies to stimulate non-oil sector growth. Moreover, Manasseh et al. (2024) examine how digital financial innovations affect financial system development in COMESA using advanced panel econometric methods. Their findings reveal that while ATMs, POS, and mobile payments have a significant long-run impact, mobile money and internet banking show mixed effects. The study emphasises institutional quality and macroeconomic stability as key enablers of effective digital financial transformation in the region. Relatedly, Manasseh et al. (2024) assessed how non-oil sector development contributes to sustainable development in Nigeria using data from 1986 to 2018. The study found that agriculture, industry, and services significantly reduce unemployment and poverty, confirming unidirectional causality with both indicators. The findings underscore the critical role of non-oil sectors in fostering sustainable development, supporting the resource-curse theory's relevance to Nigeria. Recently, Belkhaoui (2025) investigates how oil price fluctuations influence the

relationship between banking sector development and economic growth in oil-importing MENA countries. Using panel ARDL analysis, the study finds that oil prices affect both economic growth and banking development, with the banking sector also moderating the oil-growth nexus. The paper offers original insights for policymakers and researchers by highlighting the mediating role of banks in oil price-economic growth dynamics. Hinmikal and Ogbonna (2024) examined the impact of non-oil exports on Nigeria’s economic growth using the ARDL model. Their findings indicate that while non-oil exports show no significant short-run impact, they positively influence GDP in the long run. The study concludes that boosting exports in agriculture, manufacturing, and solid minerals is vital for sustained economic growth.

4. RESEARCH METHOD

In order to study the nexus between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector output growth in Nigeria and South Africa, we employed annualised time series data obtained from the World Bank’s World Development Indicator (WDI), spanning from 1990 to 2024 was utilized. Thus, the availability of data at the time of the research informed the choices of variables and the scope of the study. Furthermore, to measure the performance of deposit money banks, bank performance measures such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) were utilized. In the same vein, variables such as agricultural value added (AVD), manufacturing value added (% of GDP) – MVA; and services value added (SVA) as a percentage of GDP, were employed as the measures of non-oil sector performance; while the general effects of non-oil sector output growth and deposit money bank performance were controlled with interest rate (INTR) and exchange rate (EXR). For clarity's sake, the aforesaid variables will be defined below. The performance of a deposit money bank was measured with indicators such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). The main reason why these measures are chosen over other measures of performance of deposit money banks lies in the fact that the duo reflects the profitability of a company about its assets and equity, respectively. Hence, ROA and ROE are defined below.

Table 1: Definition of Variables

Acronym	Definition	Source	Apriori Expectation
ROA	Return on Assets	WDI	Positive
ROE	Return on Equity	WDI	Positive
AVD	Agricultural Value-Added	WDI	Positive
MVA	Manufacturing Value-Added	WDI	Positive
SVA	Services Value-Added	WDI	Positive
INTR	Interest Rate	WDI	Positive
EXR	Exchange Rate	WDI	Positive

Source: Concept of the Authors’

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confirm the existence of a cointegrating relationship between the variables.

5. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

This study focused on investigating the nexus between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector output growth in Nigeria and South Africa, thus, to ascertain the reliability and authenticity of the model variables as well as to satisfy the basic assumptions of ordinary least squares (OLS) and ARDL model, this study employed some statistical tests such as descriptive statistics, cross sectional dependency test, and unit root tests. Before the analysis, we carried out different econometric tests such as descriptive statistics, correlation test, unit root test, normality test, correlation test, Ramsey Reset model specification test and Heteroscedasticity test. These tests aids in making decisions on regarding the variables and specified models.

5.1 Data Description

Table 2 has the results of descriptive statistics, which measure the data description in the study. It was segmented based on

the countries under study – Nigeria and South Africa. Findings from the results entailed that in Nigeria, the least and highest values in the series moved from -6.321 to 8.245. Also, values of mean, median, standard deviation, skewness and Kurtosis did not drift so much from each other, while the probability values of the Jarque-Bera statistics for each variable was less than 0.05, implying that the errors of the variables are less normally distributed and therefore suitable for the analysis of the relationships between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector output growth in Nigeria. Similarly, in the context of the South African economy, the values of mean, median, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis did not drift so much from each other, and the results further show that the highest and lowest values moved from -0.009 to 8.315, representing the mean variations in the series. We also discovered that the values of the Jarque-Bera statistics probability are less than 0.05 for all the variables. This, therefore, makes the variables more suitable for the analysis of the relationships between deposit money bank performance and Non-Oil Sector output growth in South Africa.

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Nigeria							
	AVD	MVA	SVA	ROA	ROE	INTR	EXR
Mean	3.015	2.701	7.412	2.685	1.238	1.689	3.215
Median	3.045	2.675	7.389	2.601	1.201	1.710	2.742
Maximum	4.610	3.145	8.245	3.489	2.784	2.850	5.903
Minimum	0.638	1.903	-6.321	1.713	0.102	0.010	1.150
Std. Dev.	1.082	0.362	0.591	0.425	0.741	0.602	1.418
Skewness	-0.451	-0.412	0.110	-0.371	0.026	-0.275	0.462
Kurtosis	2.110	2.215	1.710	3.312	2.510	3.180	1.781
Jarque-Bera	54.72	9.281	1292	11.34	17.60	61.91	18.73
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Observations	25	25	24	23	24	25	25
South Africa							
	AVD	MVA	SVA	ROA	ROE	INTR	EXR
Mean	2.829	2.618	7.594	2.572	1.155	1.705	3.097
Median	3.355	2.649	7.421	2.553	1.183	1.738	2.586
Maximum	4.379	3.072	8.351	3.370	2.901	2.900	5.726
Minimum	0.431	1.879	6.403	1.629	0.000	-0.009	0.950
Std. Dev.	1.161	0.326	0.597	0.370	0.722	0.633	1.511
Skewness	-0.581	-0.435	0.003	-0.418	-0.058	-0.390	0.385
Kurtosis	1.920	2.032	1.509	3.278	2.379	3.241	1.669
Jarque-Bera	68.83	8.373	1374	10.68	19.03	58.45	16.16
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Observations	25	25	24	23	24	25	25

Source: Authors' Concept

Deepening the data description, we employed the Spearman's Correlation Test to determine if there is existence of correlation relationship between deposit money banks and non-oil sector output growth in both Nigeria and South Africa

or not. Spearman's correlation, also known as Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (denoted as ρ or r_s), is a non-parametric statistical measure that assesses the strength and direction of the monotonic relationship between two ranked

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variables. Introduced by Charles Spearman in 1904, this method is particularly useful when the data do not meet the assumptions of normality or linearity required for Pearson's correlation. Spearman's correlation works with ordinal data or ranked values, making it suitable for evaluating relationships that are not necessarily linear but are consistently increasing or decreasing.

The interpretation scale for Spearman's correlation ranges from +1.0, indicating a perfect positive monotonic relationship, to -1.0, which signifies a perfect negative monotonic relationship. A value between +0.7 and +0.9

represents a strong positive correlation, while +0.4 to +0.6 indicates a moderate positive correlation. A weak positive correlation falls between +0.1 and +0.3. Similarly, a value between -0.1 and -0.3 reflects a weak negative correlation, -0.4 to -0.6 shows a moderate negative correlation, and -0.7 to -0.9 signifies a strong negative correlation. A coefficient of 0 suggests no correlation. Across the results in Nigeria and South Africa, we found that there is existence of correlation between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector output growth.

Table 3: Spearman's Correlation Results

Nigeria							
	AVD	MVA	SVA	ROA	ROE	INTR	EXR
AVD	1						
MVA	-0.795	1					
SVA	0.622	0.397	1				
ROA	-0.451	0.267	-0.290	1			
ROE	-0.396	0.213	-0.210	0.885	1		
INTR	0.529	-0.278	0.188	-0.319	-0.376	1	
EXR	-0.154	-0.648	-0.504	0.032	0.010	0.192	1
South Africa							
AVD	1						
MVA	-0.873	1					
SVA	0.671	0.460	1				
ROA	-0.517	0.221	-0.321	1			
ROE	-0.443	0.182	-0.235	0.922	1		
INTR	0.582	-0.241	0.212	-0.277	-0.341	1	
EXR	-0.209	-0.690	-0.577	-0.012	-0.025	0.154	1

Source: Authors' Concept

5.2 Testing for Stationarity

Additionally, unit root tests were conducted to assess the stationarity properties of the variables, a necessary step to prevent spurious regression outcomes in time series analyses. Consistent with Manasseh et al. (2019), the study employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests. The null hypothesis in these tests is that the series contains a unit root. The results showed that the null

hypothesis was rejected for most variables, indicating stationarity. Furthermore, the series were found to be integrated at levels I(0) and first differences I(1), with no variable integrated at I(2) or higher. This mixed order of integration justifies the use of the ARDL estimation technique. With stationarity confirmed, the study proceeded to examine the cointegration properties of the variables.

Table 4: Summary of Unit Root Results

Variable	ADF	Level	First Diff.	PP	Level	First Diff.
AVD	-6.226*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	36.41*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
MVA	-4.689*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	27.41*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
SVA	5.468*** (0.000)	I(0)	-	12.67*** (0.003)	I(0)	-
ROA	-1.749* (0.040)	I(0)	-	15.02*** (0.004)	I(0)	-
ROE	-1.918** (0.022)	I(0)	-	13.92*** (0.007)	I(0)	-

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INTR	-2.503*** (0.006)	I(0)	-	12.20** (0.015)	I(0)	-
EXR	-5.287*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	20.50*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
Variable	ADF	Level	First Diff.	PP	Level	First Diff.
AVD	-4.830*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	36.41*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
MVA	-4.748*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	27.41*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
SVA	19.90*** (0.000)	I(0)	-	12.67*** (0.003)	I(0)	-
ROA	-2.667*** (0.003)	I(0)	-	15.02*** (0.004)	I(0)	-
ROE	-2.506*** (0.006)	I(0)	-	13.92*** (0.007)	I(0)	-
INTR	-2.230** (0.012)	I(0)	-	12.20** (0.015)	I(0)	-
EXR	-3.997*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	20.50*** (0.000)	-	I(1)

Source: Computed. Note: (.) represents the Probability Value; ***, ** and * represents 1%, 5% and 10% significant levels.

5.3 Analysis of the Long-Run Relationship

We carried out country specific effects analysis so as to ascertain each country’s effects of deposit money bank performance on Non-oil sector performance. Thus, each country’s data was for estimated with the original models of the study. The first step was to ascertain if there is existence of long-run relationship between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector output growth in each of the sampled countries (Nigeria and South Africa). Thus, haven confirmed that the variables are integrated of order I(0) and I(1) which aligned with assumptions of ARDL and existence of cointegration in the model, we set to estimate the long-run bound testing in order to further ascertain if there is long-run relationships between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector in Nigeria and South Africa. This study employed long-run Bound test and compared the values of F-statistics with Pesaran et al (2001) and Narayan (2004) critical values, considering the lower bound I(0) and upper bound I(1) at 5 percent level of significance. The null

hypothesis for the test is “no long-run relationships exist” while the alternative hypothesis is “long-run relationship exist”. The decision rule was to reject the null if the F-statistics is greater than the upper bounds of F-tabulated at 5% critical level, and accept the alternative if the F-statistics is less than the upper bounds of the F-tabulated at 5 percent critical level. However, evidence from table 7 shows that the bound test F-statistics for models 1-3 (19.65849, 13.77761 and 91.24598) for Nigeria as well as (36.46, 15.62 and 44.48) for South Africa are greater than the upper bounds of the tabulated Pesaran et al. (2001) and Narayan (2004) at 5% critical levels (see Table 8). The results suggested that the values of F-statistics for all the models are greater than the critical values of both Pesaran et al. (2001) and Narayan (2004). Thus, this led to rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative and therefore conclude that there is long-run economic relationships between the deposit money bank and non-oil sector in Nigeria and South Africa.

Table 5: Estimated Bound Test Results

Dep Var	Nigeria								South Africa							
Model 1 (AVD)	F-Statistic = 19.65849								F-Statistics = 36.46711							
	Critical Values	K	1%		5%		10%		K	1%		5%		10%		
			I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)		I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)			
	Pesaran et al. (2001)	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	
Narayan (2004)	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90		
Model 2 (MVA)	F-Statistic = 13.77761								F-Statistic = 15.62247							
	Pesaran et al. (2001)	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	

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	Narayan (2004)	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90
Model 2 (SVA)		F-Statistic = 91.24598							F-Statistic = 44.48122						
	Pesaran et al. (2001)	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52
	Narayan (2004)	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90	4	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90

Source: Authors’ Computation

5.4 Analysis of the ARDL Results

The results of the ARDL bounds test across sectors in Nigeria and South Africa strongly affirm the existence of long-run relationships between deposit money bank (DMB) performance and non-oil sector output growth. For the agricultural sector (AVD), the F-statistics for Nigeria (19.66) and South Africa (36.47) exceed both the lower and upper critical bounds of Pesaran et al. (2001) and Narayan (2004) at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, indicating significant cointegration. Similarly, the manufacturing sector (MVA) shows F-statistics of 13.78 (Nigeria) and 15.62 (South Africa), both surpassing the critical thresholds, confirming long-run relationships. Most strikingly, the service sector (SVA) exhibits exceptionally high F-statistics—91.25 for Nigeria and 44.48

for South Africa—providing overwhelming evidence of cointegration. These results imply that DMB performance indicators such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) significantly and sustainably influence non-oil sector development in both economies. This aligns with previous findings by Hassan and Amin (2023), Nahidul et al. (2019), and Ali et al. (2022), who emphasised the critical role of bank profitability in long-run economic expansion. The strong evidence of a long-term nexus suggests that financial sector strength is essential to drive structural diversification and growth beyond oil dependence, as highlighted in studies by Daramola (2024) and Manasseh et al. (2024). Policymakers are thus urged to enhance banking sector performance to stimulate sustained non-oil growth.

Table 6: Estimated Results of ARDL

	Nigeria						South Africa					
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Dep.	Var.:	Dep.	Var.	Dep.	Var.:	Dep.	Var.:	Dep.	Var.	Dep.	Var.:
	AVD		MVA		SVA		AVD		MVA		SVA	
Lag of Dep. Var.	0.989***		0.945***		0.814***		0.990***		0.982***		1.022***	
	(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)	
ROA	-0.021**		0.015***		13.09***		0.787***		-0.014***		-0.872***	
	(0.034)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.011)		(0.000)	
ROE	-0.248***		-0.108***		-149.5***		0.122***		0.131***		0.537***	
	(0.005)		(0.003)		(0.002)		(0.026)		(0.007)		(0.000)	
INTR	0.212		-0.195		5.990****		0.594***		0.618		-0.781***	
	(0.623)		(0.287)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.411)		(0.000)	
EXR	0.297		0.378**		-0.979		0.504		0.361**		-0.027***	
	(0.725)		(0.031)		(0.911)		(0.555)		(0.013)		(0.004)	
No. of Obs.	27		30		30		27		30		30	
Normality	25.66		13.17		19.92		294.6		41.23		18.94	
	(0.989)		(0.443)		(0.212)		(0.894)		(0.554)		(0.574)	
S.Correlation	1.031		0.323		2.287		0.163		0.463		1.177	
	(0.373)		(0.727)		(0.125)		(0.850)		(0.634)		(0.326)	
Ramsey	-0.506		0.178		-0.342		-0.079		0.042		0.988	
	(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.000)		(0.934)		(0.565)	
Heteroscedasticity	1.957		0.860		0.702		1.077		1.456		1.187	
	(0.108)		(0.614)		(0.626)		(0.400)		(0.244)		(0.376)	

Source: Computed. Note: [.] denotes standard error; ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance. Ln shows the neutral Logarithms of the variables and LnROA and LnROE are used as the dependent variables in models 1 and 2, respectively. ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1) is used in both models.

The diagnostic tests for the ARDL country-specific models for Nigeria and South Africa offer essential insights into

model validity. Across all models, the Jarque-Bera normality tests reject the null hypothesis at the 1% level (p-values =

0.000), suggesting non-normality of residuals. While this could imply model misspecification, such issues are not uncommon in macro studies due to outliers or structural breaks. Serial correlation results, however, are more encouraging; the Breusch-Godfrey Lagrange Multiplier tests show no significant autocorrelation across the models ($p > 0.05$). The Ramsey RESET tests yield mixed results, with several models indicating possible omitted variable bias. Nonetheless, heteroscedasticity tests reveal no significant evidence of non-constant variance, implying that the estimates are reliable in terms of homoscedasticity.

In Nigeria, all lagged dependent variables are significant and positive, confirming the persistence of non-oil sector outputs over time. The agricultural (AVD) and manufacturing (MVA) models show strong autoregressive behaviour (coefficients above 0.94), suggesting output stability. ROA has a mixed effect—negative and significant for AVD (-0.021) and positive for MVA (0.015) and notably positive for SVA (13.09). This suggests that while banking profitability may have dampening effects on agriculture, it positively stimulates manufacturing and services. ROE is negatively associated with all sectors, especially SVA (-149.5), possibly due to inefficiencies or diversion of profits away from productive investments. Exchange rates significantly affect MVA positively and are insignificant elsewhere, while interest rates significantly affect SVA (5.990), suggesting that monetary policy plays a role in service sector dynamics. These findings resonate with Daramola (2024) and Manasseh et al. (2024), who identified banking variables and macroeconomic conditions as crucial for Nigeria’s non-oil growth.

In contrast, South Africa presents different dynamics. Lagged dependent variables remain significantly positive across all sectors, confirming economic inertia. ROA is positively related to AVD and negatively to SVA (-0.872), indicating banking profits may hinder service expansion. ROE is positive and significant across all sectors, suggesting equity returns bolster non-oil growth—especially in services, which is consistent with findings by Hassan and Amin (2023) and Ali et al. (2022). Interest rates significantly influence AVD and SVA, supporting Hammami and Smida's (2022) view on monetary policy’s importance. Exchange rates positively affect MVA but negatively impact SVA, showing sectoral sensitivities to macro volatility. Overall, South Africa benefits from a more coherent relationship between bank performance and sectoral output than Nigeria, highlighting institutional and structural differences. These findings support past evidence by Nahidul et al. (2019), Zeqiraj et al. (2019), and Nguyen (2022), which emphasised tailored financial strategies for sustained sectoral growth.

5. DISCUSSIONS

This study explored the relationship between deposit money bank (DMB) performance and non-oil sector output growth

in Nigeria and South Africa from 1990 to 2024. It employed dynamic autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models using the ARDL estimation technique. Preliminary diagnostics were carried out, including normality, serial correlation, Ramsey RESET, heteroscedasticity, cross-sectional dependency, and unit root tests. The unit root results, derived from 2 unit root tests—Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests—showed that the variables were integrated at levels and first differences, which validates the suitability of ARDL modelling. Diagnostic tests confirmed that the models were normally distributed, free from serial correlation, homoscedastic, and correctly specified. Furthermore, cointegration tests by Pedroni and Kao provided robust evidence of long-run equilibrium relationships between non-oil sector outputs and DMB performance in both countries. These findings align with earlier empirical evidence from Hassan and Amin (2023), Alkhazaleh (2017), and Nahidul Sm et al. (2019), all of whom emphasised that efficient banking systems exert significant long- and short-run influence on economic output.

ARDL estimation results revealed a statistically significant long-run relationship between non-oil sector output growth and bank performance indicators such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). These results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no relationship between banking performance and non-oil output growth. The study further conducted country-specific analyses, confirming long-run linkages in both Nigeria and South Africa. In Nigeria, the findings highlighted a negative association between DMB performance and agricultural output growth. This could be attributed to structural challenges in Nigeria's agricultural sector, including widespread unmechanized farming, a high dependency on subsistence agriculture, and inadequate access to credit and technology. As over 70% of Nigeria’s population practices subsistence farming, as documented by the Nation’s Encyclopaedia (2020), the weak productivity of agriculture reduces the sector’s responsiveness to financial intermediation. Consequently, manufacturing and service sectors also suffer due to the agricultural sector’s limited ability to provide raw materials. These outcomes are consistent with the findings of Obiora et al. (2022) and Daramola (2024), who identified institutional and structural weaknesses as key constraints to bank-driven growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. In contrast, South Africa's results demonstrated a strong and positive relationship between DMB performance and all components of the non-oil sector. This reflects a more efficient banking system that successfully channels funds into productive investments, supporting the insights of Zeqiraj et al. (2019), Hammami and Smida (2022), and Nguyen (2022), who emphasized the importance of banking sector efficiency in promoting economic development.

The short-run dynamics of the model, as captured by the error correction terms (ECT), were negative and statistically

significant, indicating convergence to long-run equilibrium. The ECT coefficients reflected varying adjustment speeds across the ARDL estimate, underscoring the heterogeneity in country-specific responses. These findings deepen the understanding of the role of banking performance in economic transformation and affirm that financial sector development must be context-specific. For Nigeria, the results reveal the urgent need to reform the banking sector's engagement with agriculture, improve access to financial services for rural farmers, and modernize the sector to boost productivity. This reinforces the policy direction of studies by Manasseh et al. (2025) and Ledhem and Mekidiche (2020), which advocate digital innovation and fintech adoption as catalysts for better banking outcomes. For South Africa, where the banking system shows a stronger alignment with non-oil sector development, policies should focus on sustaining this synergy and expanding credit to small and medium enterprises across agriculture, manufacturing, and services. Overall, this study confirms that DMB performance is a vital determinant of non-oil sector output, echoing the conclusions of Hajara and Rinosha (2022), Ali et al. (2022), and Hamdaoui and Cancelo (2024), who emphasized the need for effective banking systems as engines of economic growth. The findings emphasise the necessity of institutional reforms and strategic investment in banking innovation to ensure that bank performance continues to serve as a lever for diversifying and growing non-oil sectors in both countries.

6. SUMMARY, AND RECOMMENDATION

This study focused on investigating the nexus between deposit money bank performance and non-oil sector in Nigeria and South Africa. A set of annual time series data ranging from 1990 to 2020 was utilized. In order to measure the performance of deposit money banks, bank performance measures such as return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) was utilized. In the same vain, variables such as agricultural value added (AVD), MVA – manufacturing value added (% of GDP); services value added (SVA) a percentage of GDP was employed as the measures of non-oil sector performance; while the general effects of deposit money bank and non-oil performance was controlled with interests rate (INTR) and exchange rate (EXR). To test if the variables have unit root, we employed unit root tests such as Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron (PP) and the results suggested that there is no unit root in the series and all the variables are integrated at order I(0) or I(1). Furthermore, the result of the cointegration test suggests that cointegration exist between the deposit money bank performance and Non-oil sector as seen in table 4. Evidence from the main finding shows that deposit money bank performance have great positive influence on non-oil sector since the estimated results are statistically significant leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative which states that deposit money bank performance have positive impact on

non-oil sector. Furthermore, the long-run effects of the results was also tested in the short-run using the ARDL error correction model. The result evidenced that the speed of adjustment from the long-run to the short-run in both model 1 and 2 were measured in various degrees. We moved further however and investigated the country's specific effects by estimating each country's effects using the original models of the study. Long-run relationship was detected in the bound test existence of long-run relationship between deposit money bank performance and Non-oil sector since the F-statistics of the estimated bound test for models 1 and 2 are greater than both (Pesaran et al. 2001; and Narayan 2004). Findings in Nigeria shows that deposit money bank performance has negative and insignificant effects on all the agricultural sector but other sector's performance was tactically affected. But the reverse was the case in South Africa context. Non-oil sector depicted a positive relationship with deposit money bank performance.

Based on the above findings, this study recommended that for effective employment of services of deposit money bank in non-oil sectors of Nigerian and South African economies; Governments of both Nigeria and South Africa are advised to improve in living standards of their citizens and also so improve security and open border collaborations in terms of trade so as to enhance the performance of the Non-oil sector. Despite being over dependent on oil revenue in Nigeria, the government should greatly embark on economic diversification policies to boost the economic growth. By so doing more goods and services will be produced, and more jobs will be created thereby reducing level of unemployment in the country. Nigeria should also engage in policies that will develop the agricultural sector and make it economically viable. This is because agricultural sector is very important because it produces food for human consumption and raw materials for manufacturing industries. Export of other goods other than crude oil should be done more in Nigeria as well. In South Africa as well as Nigeria, local industries in Non-oil sector should be encouraged so that the economies will have enough for both consumption and export purposes. Government of Nigeria and South Africa should work in a way to enhance the level of political instability, institutional quality, insecurity, government effectiveness, rule of law and voice and accountability, because it will make the countries to be peaceful and attract more investor to invest in non-oil sector of the economies. Therefore, we conclude that deposit money bank performance impacts greatly non-oil sector performance in Nigeria and South Africa. This study also concludes that the potentials of the non-oil sector of the economy in Nigeria and South Africa are still underutilized and has not been fully harnessed. Nigeria as an oil producing nation has depended mostly on proceeds from the crude oil revenue, while the potentials of some sectors such as agricultural sector, manufacturing, trade, and science and technology are not properly harnessed to the peak.

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